

IN-HABIT - INclusive Health And wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies

D2.1 Inclusive Transformation Plan of Āgenskalns market area in Riga

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32	Section 5.1 updated with paragraph about the involvement of different groups in the co-design stage.
35-39	Section 5.3 updated with additional information about the planned implementation of the VIS.

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Executive summary

The main goal of the Riga team in IN-HABIT is to promote healthy and inclusive communities in Āgenskalns neighbourhood by developing Āgenskalns market into a multifunctional and creative urban food hub. The inclusive transformation plan (ITP) provides an overview of the initial vision (February 2022) for the development of visionary and integrated solutions in Āgenskalns market.

The organisation and governance of IN-HABIT activities in Riga have been envisaged from the outset as a set of three concentric circles. The first circle consists of the core group, the three project partners (Baltic Studies Centre, Kalnciema Quarter, Riga Planning Region). The second circle is the enlarged group, which includes the core group and a small number of development specialists and activists, and representatives of various organisations and associations. The outermost circle refers to the residents of Āgenskalns neighbourhood and other actors interested in the future development of Āgenskalns market.

The activities in the first year of operation have largely been determined by the public health situation in Latvia and the fact that the planned solutions are still at an early stage of development. The choice has been in favour of traditional methods (workshops and surveys), though they have involved a significant online component.

In general, the design of the proposed solutions was based on the recognition that Āgenskalns market is an important public space in the neighbourhood. This approach has coalesced into four main directions of work. All four are examples of incremental innovation as they are not radical departures from available solutions and build on existing examples found both locally and abroad: (i) transformation of the outdoor marketplace, (ii) community kitchen, (iii) minimisation of waste at the market, and (iv) an online food purchasing system.

Up until now the co-creation process has primarily been focused on exploring different needs and understandings of the role of Āgenskalns market, with less attention being devoted to the minutiae of implementing this vision in practice. These will be addressed in greater detail after the official opening of Āgenskalns market in April 2022.

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1. Introduction

Riga is the capital city and the largest city of Latvia. It is also the most economically developed and vibrant city in Latvia, and it consistently accounts for over half of the Latvian GDP¹. Nonetheless, the population is slowly declining, and the city faces several issues that hamper the perception of Riga as an inclusive and safe place for all social groups, leading to different experiences of the city's urban spaces (e.g. discrimination). These issues were confirmed in the initial stages of IN-HABIT (see Appendix 5) and require the development of innovative solutions focusing on health and well-being in a broad sense.

In an attempt to experiment with novel solutions that could improve urban health and well-being, the Riga team will focus its attention on Āgenskalns neighbourhood as the primary site of intervention. The historical Āgenskalns neighbourhood is currently envisaged in Riga city development plans as a residential area and place for innovative businesses, to be developed by means of advancing green infrastructure, nature-based innovations and developing science and education centres of national importance.

However, **public and private investments currently being made in the neighbourhood need to be supplemented with cultural activities and healthy lifestyle opportunities for local residents.** While Āgenskalns is well-connected to the city centre, there are limited opportunities for cultural and social life in Āgenskalns itself, particularly for families and young professionals. In addition, the presence of several pawn shops and gambling establishments, and the perception that Āgenskalns is insufficiently safe limits its social desirability. Furthermore, while the local community has been described as cohesive, the influx of students from abroad due to the proximity of Āgenskalns to several university campuses, may be seen as disrupting the social equilibrium. This, in turn, suggests a need for spaces that (i) allow individuals from various different backgrounds to interact without fear of discrimination or discomfort and (ii) are organised around broader considerations related to GDEI.

In this regard, **the success of Kalnciema Quarter (KQ – practice partner in the project) in the development of an urban quarter in Āgenskalns has shown the potential of sustainably produced and locally sourced food in (i) revitalising social and cultural life in the**

¹ For more information see: https://www.rdpad.lv/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/RD_buklets_ENG.pdf

neighbourhood in an inclusive manner and (ii) promoting health-conscious dietary habits. Now this experience is being taken forward in a new investment project, which is the primary anchor point of the Riga IN-HUB - the transformation of Āgenskalns market into an intercultural and creative food hub in collaboration with Riga City Council and Riga Planning Region (RPR) and Baltic Studies Centre (BSC).

The IN-HUB is a laboratory of social innovation where people coming from different public and private organisations, or as individual citizens work together for social change. It is a networking strategy for the enhancement of cooperation aimed at the co-design and co-management of spaces and a platform for structural dialogue and collaboration. IN-HUBs are both physical places for meeting and sharing, and organisational structures to facilitate the transformative process.

Source: IN-HABIT Glossary

The main goal of the Riga team in IN-HABIT is to promote healthy and inclusive communities in Āgenskalns neighbourhood by developing Āgenskalns market into an open and creative food hub. The distinctiveness of Riga in IN-HABIT lies in its focus on sustainable food as the basis for healthy and inclusive urban well-being. The main activities will concern the area surrounding Āgenskalns market.

An intercultural and creative food hub is a multifunctional space that is intended not only as a food hub for sustainably produced and locally sourced food, but also as a recreational and educational space. The hub aims to promote healthy and sustainable food habits, as well as social and cultural integration and cohesion, which is done by: (1) promoting healthy lifestyles and food consumption habits among local people, particularly the most vulnerable (e.g. elderly, children), and discouraging sedentary lifestyles and unhealthy diets; (2) improving accessibility for all while encouraging sustainable mobility (e.g. walking and cycling) from and to the hub; (3) using food as a means to improve intercultural and intergenerational social relations, create a sense of belonging and ownership of the place; and (4) shortening food supply chains and decreasing food waste in the market

Source: IN-HABIT glossary

The goal is to utilise the potential of the latter as a space of promoting healthy and sustainable food habits, social and cultural integration and cohesion, thereby making the neighbourhood a desirable and safe place to live and visit. In particular, work in Riga will concentrate on: (i)

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improvements of physical public infrastructure in and around the territory of Āgenskalns market in Riga, and (ii) the promotion of food related educational and consumption practices.

The link between health and wellbeing is built into the very concept of a multifunctional urban food hub. The co-creation activities as part of the visionary and integrated solutions will be geared towards food education and the popularisation of sustainable diets and consumption habits, and social and cultural activities in the neighbourhood. In practical terms, healthy lifestyles will be promoted through improved access to locally sourced products and educational classes about nutrition organised at the market, notably in the community kitchen.

The Riga IN-HUB works in lockstep with the overall vision of KQ, which has undertaken the renovation and reconstruction of Āgenskalns market and is actively investing in the market. Therefore, the activities and directions of work of the Riga IN-HUB are designed with the aim of creating synergies and complementarities between the contribution of IN-HABIT and the investor's development plans and actions.

KQ employs a flexible business model that connects commercial and socially oriented activities. This business model is characterised by the following:

- Many business activities are simultaneously economically oriented, socially focused on the inclusion of different groups, and eco-oriented towards sustainability objectives.
- A combination of food sales with social, cultural and educational activities in a renovated, accessible and attractive urban environment.
- Business practices that are open to new opportunities and dynamic cooperation with different partners, including: business partners (producers, processors, traders, buyers, other SMEs), public partners (municipalities, public authorities), civil society partners (neighbourhood associations NGOs, interest groups), and science and education partners (universities, research institutes, schools).
- A diverse range of funding sources: private investment, public co-financing for development and innovation projects, funding for social entrepreneurship, borrowing, income from renting premises and other sources of funding. In some cases, voluntary work and other forms of social participation are relied upon.

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- Active work on the image and reputation of the project, which contributes to public recognition of the market, promoting consumer engagement and improving credibility in the eyes of financial partners and public institutions.

The synergy between the market and IN-HABIT is an important aspect to build upon. It provides value added to market activities that otherwise would have remained limited in terms of impact. IN-HABIT brings international expertise and methodologies for developing particular activities, whereas the market itself provides the physical space and infrastructure to embed the VIS and a team that is respected by local stakeholders. This allows the pilot to connect to other innovative actions in the neighbourhood and the city as a whole. Furthermore, an additional aim is to transfer and popularise the Riga IN-HUB experience in other cities in Latvia. To achieve this aim, RPR will use its policy networks to spread information and best practices developed in Āgenskalns market to other municipalities in Latvia.

The inclusive transformation plan (ITP) provides an overview of the initial vision (February 2022) for the development of Āgenskalns market, insight into how this vision was developed (and with whom), and some tentative lessons that can be drawn from this process. The process has primarily focused on exploring different needs and understandings of the role of Āgenskalns market in the neighbourhood and Riga more generally, with less attention being devoted to the minutiae of implementing this vision in practice. These will be addressed in greater detail after the official opening of Āgenskalns market in April 2022.

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2. IN-HUB establishment: organisation, methods and achievements

2.1. Establishment of core project team & stakeholder mapping

The core project team consists of Riga's three project partners (see below). After the official start of the project in September 2020, the core team discussed and agreed upon the partners' main responsibilities and forms of communication. The core team had its first planning meeting on 2 November 2020. The team has further agreed on the roles and responsibilities of the individual members. Nonetheless, while each partner has their primary responsibilities, all are involved in the day-to-day work of the project in some form and participate in project meetings.

KQ is the main practice partner. KQ manages an urban quarter² that regularly hosts cultural and business events, such as festivals, concerts, film screening, exhibitions, and design shops, as well as a popular and prominent weekly farmers' and artisanal market. KQ's team is in charge of (i) implementing the Āgenskalns market renovation and modernisation project and, (ii) drawing on a range of previously established contacts and relations, facilitating stakeholder engagement.

BSC is the research partner. It is a private non-profit research organisation. The main areas of BSC expertise include food system and food supply chain analysis; food and nutrition security; agricultural knowledge and innovation systems; sustainable territorial development processes and policies. BSC's team coordinates, monitors and documents all IN-HUB activities, and facilitates stakeholder engagement with the help of KQ.

The public partner RPR is one of five planning regions in Latvia, and their responsibility is the planning and coordination of socio-economic development in the greater Riga region. RPR will act as a bridge to other municipalities and municipal agendas in the greater Riga planning region. RPR is primarily responsible for achieving policy and planning impact.

The core group has established a rhythm of meeting once every two weeks. Meeting minutes are prepared to maintain a log of all topics discussed and decisions made during the meetings.

² For more information see: <http://www.kalnciemaiela.lv/en/>

Meeting minutes are stored online in a password-protected cloud folder that is owned and managed by BSC.

In the initial meetings of the core team, **a stakeholder mapping exercise was carried out**. The core team identified several stakeholder groups (see Annex 1) that will likely be affected by the development of Āgenskalns market and should be approached to participate in co-creation exercises and join the User Advisory Board (see below). Furthermore, their potential role and interest in the development of Āgenskalns market was also discussed to ensure that they could be involved in the project at the appropriate moment.

It was agreed that the primary stakeholders who should be directly involved in the project are the **residents of Āgenskalns** and the **neighbourhood association of Āgenskalns**. However, the variety of organisations and individuals identified was quite broad, ranging from environmental NGOs and entrepreneurs who are active in the neighbourhood, to state and municipal institutions. These stakeholders have been and will continue to be approached to participate in IN-HABIT events and co-creation workshops. It should be noted, however, that, while all have been approached to participate in various IN-HABIT activities and events, **COVID-19 related restrictions have forced the core team to organise many of the activities online, potentially hampering the participation of some groups (e.g. senior citizens)** who are not active users of the chosen platforms, meaning that their needs have yet to be fully taken into account.

In addition, the stakeholder mapping exercise allowed the core team to identify the range of interests that should ideally be represented on the User Advisory Board by different organisations and NGOs.

2.2. Open call and communication campaign to select the members of the local IN-HUB

In addition to the core project team, the Riga IN-HUB established a User Advisory Board (UAB). The members of the UAB were selected via an open call (call text available in Latvian [Appendix 4]), meaning that in principle anyone could join the advisory board. The call was organised in January and February 2021, and primarily circulated via the social media profiles of the institutions constituting the core team in Riga. Applicants had to indicate their commitment to the project by submitting a letter describing their interest in relation to the stated goals of IN-

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HABIT in Riga. Other members, whose role in the Riga IN-HUB is situational, are approached more opportunistically, depending on the needs of particular activities. However, the chosen method of communication is almost invariably social media, with some cases of organisations or individuals being approached individually due to their expertise.

2.3. Assignment of specific roles (local community activators/representatives, UAB, thematic sub-groups) and their activities

The organisation and governance of the Riga IN-HUB, and IN-HABIT activities in Riga more generally, have been envisaged from the outset as a set of three concentric circles of actors who carry out their tasks by interacting among themselves and by networking with other stakeholders, while being primarily driven by the vision of the core team. This approach allows for structure and continuity, while simultaneously designing in regular feedback from stakeholders not directly involved in the project and continuous revision of ideas proposed by the core team in general, and the practice partner (KQ) in particular. This decision derives from the specific nature of the IN-HABIT interventions in Riga, which will take place in Āgenskalns market, a neighbourhood market currently managed by a private company (KQ).

Riga IN-HUB

The first circle consists of the core group. The core team consists of three project partners who have agreed on their roles and responsibilities. The core group has meetings about once every two weeks to discuss ongoing activities and plan future events.

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The second circle is the enlarged group, which includes the members of the core group and a small number of development specialists and activists, and representatives of various organisations and associations. This is exemplified by the UAB, which consists of the core team and ten individuals not directly involved in the project. As noted above, members of the UAB were recruited via an open call. The first meeting took place in March 2021. Subsequently, a memorandum of cooperation was drafted to agree upon principles of collaboration, and statutes were prepared to organise work in the advisory board (see supplementary documents).

Members of the UAB come from different organisations and represent different stakeholder groups, some of which are at risk of social discrimination and exclusion. The following organisations/institutions are represented: NGO Green Freedom, NGO Mozaika, Permaculture association, Āgenskalns neighbourhood association, Riga City Council, SMEs and local businesses, architects, social entrepreneurs. In practice, members of the UAB also act as community representatives as many of the organisations represented on the UAB were also identified in the stakeholder mapping exercise. Consequently, in addition to their responsibilities on the UAB, they are also involved in outreach activities and ensuring that a GDEI perspective is present at all stages of the project.

It was initially planned that four thematic sub-groups would be created within the UAB to work on the four areas of work (See Section 5). However, this idea was postponed due to there not being sufficient detail for the members of the UAB to discuss at dedicated meetings in the first year of operation. Furthermore, restrictions due to COVID-19 introduced significant delays in the operation of Āgenskalns market, so the official opening of the market had to be postponed until April 2022. This meant that interaction between the core team and the UAB took place primarily online (via email or video conferencing tools) and the market itself was akin to a virtual entity with nigh limitless potential, meaning that different options could be discussed and explored. In view of this, a more situational approach to stakeholder engagement was adopted by the core team, with exchanges taking place primarily via email and UAB members participating in IN-HABIT activities as much as their schedule allowed and when the need arose.

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Key moments in Riga IN-HUB

2 November 2020	First Riga Team meeting
3 December 2020	First Creative workshop with community representatives
31 March 2021	First UAB meeting
19 August 2021	Public discussion: E-commerce and food
26 August 2021	Public discussion: Waste as a resource
7 October 2021	First focus group on well-being in Āgenskalns
November 2021-February 2022	Community surveys about main directions of work
1 February 2022	First site visit to Āgenskalns market with the UAB
15 February 2022	UAB meetings to discuss preliminary results of community survey

The outermost circle refers to the residents of Āgenskalns neighbourhood and other actors interested in the future development of Āgenskalns market. This is the most loosely defined “circle” as it includes everyone participating in activities aimed at generating ideas for the future of Āgenskalns as part of IN-HABIT. Despite its identity being less clear, this circle has been regularly involved in IN-HABIT activities (e.g. co-creation workshops, community survey) and has been a regular source of input that allowed the core team to revise the initial plans for Āgenskalns market.

Local community activators were selected from the core team and have undergone the necessary training. The decision to delegate this responsibility to members of the core team was largely determined by expediency. Specifically, it was recognised that the workflow of Riga’s IN-HUB required someone familiar with the project and a good working relationship with the KQ team and their network of contacts. Both community activators participated in the training events organised by Tesseract to acquire the necessary skill to facilitate co-creation.

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2.4. Setting up principles, procedures, and processes of collaborative development and participation

The principles of collaborative development in the Riga IN-HUB have been developed gradually, responding to different unforeseen challenges. While this strategy was not chosen deliberately, it was agreed by the core team that the unpredictable public health situation in Latvia, limitations on public gatherings and the perceived hesitance of people to socialise outside informal circles would severely hamper any attempt to organise events at the market. This meant that, by necessity, collaboration and co-creation would be mediated by digital and video conferencing tools.

Interactions between the core team, the UAB and other parties interested in the future of Āgenskalns market have been irregular and primarily organised around specific IN-HABIT activities. While the core team meets on a regular basis, the involvement of other stakeholders has been shaped by the desire to respect the UAB's other professional commitments³. Furthermore, even though all IN-HABIT events and activities have been planned in a timely manner, they have not taken place according to a fixed schedule, as this was not deemed necessary.

The core team generally takes the initiative in proposing an activity or event. This is largely due to the fact that the organisations in question developed the initial plans for the development of the market. In view of this, the core team acts as a kind of steering committee, proposing ideas for activities, events and dates for gatherings. The UAB is involved in the capacity of an advisor at the invitation of the chairperson, who is also a member of the core team. Members of the outermost circle are sporadically consulted and provide input that allows the core team and the UAB to revise their initial ideas.

Despite the core team's taking the lead in developing the format, the UAB and other stakeholders (outermost circle) are heavily involved in developing the substance of the vision for Āgenskalns market. In the first year of operation, the core team, in collaboration with transversal IN-HABIT partners, has been in charge of selecting the methods and techniques by which different stakeholders should be engaged in the process of co-creation (e.g. hybrid

³ The core team decided early on that the use of financial incentives would be inappropriate.

workshops in August 2021). However, the overall idea has been to provide structure to the process, without limiting what ideas can be expressed at these events.

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3. Co-design of visionary and integrated solutions (VIS): top-down driven process

3.1. Working methods and management of the Toolkit

The overall approach for developing visionary and integrated solutions (VIS) in the Riga IN-HUB is heavily influenced and shaped by the *Toolkit for Stakeholders' Engagement with a Gender, Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion perspective* developed for training local community activators (LCAs). The toolkit provides a set of guidelines, methods and tools for the wider engagement of stakeholders in the people-public-private partnerships (PPPPs) that will be developed in the Riga IN-HUB. It includes instructions for stakeholder mapping and local needs assessment, selection criteria, incentives mechanisms, structure, working rules and diversity management procedures, co-design methodology, and the necessary guidelines and templates for the creation and management of the local IN-HUB.

The Toolkit has underpinned and will continue to shape an inclusive process of co-creation, co-design, co-management, and co-monitoring of the innovative solutions envisioned by the local PPPPs, with specific attention at the engagement of less represented and more at-risk-of-exclusion stakeholders. The templates provided to LCAs have been employed to reflect on the work of the IN-HUB, while the methods and tools proposed in the Toolkit will be actively deployed as part of further work in Āgenskalns market when it becomes possible to organise regular face-to-face meetings.

3.2. Training of LCAs in working methods

The core team selected two of its members to participate in a training programme developed for LCAs. The training took place online (Zoom video conferencing tool) in March and April 2021. The aim of the training programme was to equip LCAs with the skills necessary to act as community leaders and facilitate change in their local context, primarily via exposure to the principles of co-design, citizen engagement, GDEI, mindset change, communication, and impact assessment methodologies and tools. The training in project methods was five days long and organised and delivered by transversal partners (TSR, UREAD, DFC, ISIM, BOT).

The LCA training included the following modules:

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1. Understanding the transformation process in IN-HABIT: Get together; Frame 4 change; Urban reconnaissance; IHW impact evaluation methods and tools.
2. Gender, diversity, equity and inclusion (GDEI) approach; Setting the I in IHW; GDEI approach; Inclusive evaluation in practice, incentives and ethical considerations; Stakeholder mapping.
3. Communication and storytelling: capturing inputs for communication; local communication plans and tools; storytelling for inclusion; impact assessment through storytelling.
4. From vision to co-design: assessing the co-suffix; thread mapping; co-creating; I Can Mindset;
5. Managing the IN-HUB: purpose and management; GDEI Stakeholder Engagement Toolkit; local action planning.

3.3. Co-design of IHW indicators

During the initial phase of the project, transversal partner ISIM developed a set of context-based subjective and objective Inclusive Health and Well-being indicators (IHW indicators) for Riga in cooperation with local researchers and residents. The selection of IHW indicators followed an iterative and participative process which allowed for the combination of a theoretical perspective with the context-based perspective of local researchers and residents. The co-design started with a literature review and the theoretical conceptualisation of inclusive health and well-being. The initial results were then refined and validated through an iterative co-design process. In this process, the results of each step were used to revise and validate the previous choices and to refine knowledge on the local context and expected changes in terms of inclusive health and well-being in Riga. This helped researchers identify the expectations and needs of the target groups of the visionary and integrated solutions through the inclusion of citizens' point of view, especially of those representing groups at risk of discrimination and exclusion.

The participative process primarily concerned the dimensions of social well-being, economic well-being and healthy lifestyles, while mental health indicators were proposed by project partner UREAD. Although mental health indicators were not explicitly addressed in the co-design process, their relevance and their connection to the foreseen visionary and integrated solutions has also been explored.

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The perspective of local residents was considered in two steps of the process, both coordinated by ISIM and BSC - the co-design workshops with inhabitants and a survey sent to the representatives of GDEI organisations. The aim of the workshops was to discuss the most significant expected changes regarding health and well-being from the perspective of local inhabitants. Workshop guidelines were distributed by ISIM to the partners, and the Riga workshop was held online on 3 December 2020. In addition, a semi-structured questionnaire was distributed to local NGOs active in the field of GDEI policies.

The online workshop in Riga on 3 December 2020 highlighted several key aspects that should be considered by the local IN-HABIT team. Among the participants of the workshop, four were members of local neighbourhood associations and NGOs, two were students, one was a member of the city council, and one was a representative of a private business. The participants identified the following key aspects as contributing to their health and well-being:

- Appropriate infrastructure (e.g. dog parks, cycle paths, green infrastructure, children's playground, places to exercise, park benches)
- A pleasant and safe environment (e.g. clean air, no noise pollution)
- Public spaces that are available for different uses by local residents
- Public transport that is convenient and safe
- Cultural events (e.g. festivals, outdoor activities for families)
- Educational opportunities for different social and economic groups
- Social security and availability of social services
- Support (financial and otherwise) for local NGOs and small businesses
- Better public understanding of what is important in everyday life
- Opportunities to participate in shaping the future of the neighbourhood
- An active, tolerant and supportive community
- Availability of locally grown food
- Urban gardening
- Opportunities to co-create and express oneself

In the final phase, the core team participated in the empirical definition of the city specific “value chains” describing “solutions, target groups and expected changes” and finalise the list of indicators. This exercise involved revising a list of indicators with the aim of identifying

and testing the interrelations between the visionary and integrated solutions (grouped by type), the changes that these solutions may realistically produce to people's health and well-being and the set of key impact indicators identified. Based on the local value chains as well as on the results of consultations with local residents, a further revision of the IHW Indicators was performed by ISIM. The final set of IHW Indicators was produced and shared with the city partners for their final validation.

3.4. Secondary data collection

As part of the impact assessment exercise, transversal partner ISIM analysed secondary data (open data, administrative data and available statistics) with the help of city partners BSC and RPR. This activity will be carried out twice (ex-ante and ex-post) during the project and it will be used for the analysis of the city context with the twofold aim of (i) better interpretation of the IN-HABIT results and (ii) discounting external factors that may have contributed to the changes affecting inhabitants' IHW.

In the initial exercise, secondary data were collected by city partners and analysed by ISIM. In order to support city partners in the collection of secondary data for the baseline study, ISIM and UREAD provided guidance and support by delivering:

- a list of indicators for IHW specifically designed for the collection of secondary data;
- written guidelines for local public authorities on how to collect secondary data, also considering GDEI data. For each dimension/indicator, the production of data disaggregated by age, gender, and - where available — other GDEI personal characteristics has been required;
- organising meetings and informative sessions to offer support and assistance to the city partners in case of need.

Secondary data collection is based on the more general capability and functioning approach.

The capabilities approach argues that freedom of choice is the most appropriate parameter for enabling people to make valuable choices. The consequence of this theoretical approach is the proposal for a prospective change in "welfare", in which capabilities and functioning are the objectives of public policies. Starting from these theoretical premises, for each city the collection of secondary data on inhabitants - distinguished by GDEI personal characteristics - started from the selection of dimensions and indicators directly connected to well-being.

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Gathering secondary data for the ex-ante exercise proved to be challenging in Riga. The first challenge was that data for several indicators was not available, meaning that the database was incomplete – only about 2/3 of all the necessary data could be found. The second challenge was that, even in cases where data was available, it was not disaggregated by the necessary categories. This was particularly evident with regard to the disaggregation of data by neighbourhood. The primary reason is likely that, while the administrative borders of neighbourhoods are fixed, neighbourhoods are not administrative units in Riga, though they are used in planning. We also noted that data disaggregated by ethnicity, sexual orientation and type of disability was also frequently unavailable.

3.5. GDEI determinants of spatial and functional elements/or Gendered landscape

GDEI stands for Gender, Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion, and it is a key aspect of the IN-HABIT project and emphasises a fair distribution of health and well-being to everybody and strategies to reduce the gap for those at major risk of exclusion. The GDEI approach has an important part in all phases and tasks of the project, from the co-definition of impact and IHW indicators to the implementation of solutions in Āgenskalns market.

Gendered landscape questions the design of the urban space and its effects through men and women's different experiences and improves inclusivity across three pillars:

- Institutions: mainstreaming gender and diversity in administrative processes.
- Lived experiences: understanding the extent to which the cities are lived differently by different social groups, and design an effective urban space.
- Health and wellbeing inequality: mapping the extent of inequality in health and well-being in the cities to understand how urban design affects health and well-being.

This aspect will be addressed when designing the implementation of visionary and integrated solutions in Āgenskalns market.

3.6. Baseline study on IHW

For assessing the impact of IN-HABIT in terms of changes to the health and well-being of people in the re-designed city areas, it was necessary to measure and isolate the changes produced by the project compared to a baseline. A baseline study is an analysis of the current

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situation to identify the starting points for a programme or project. It looks at what information must be considered and analysed to establish a starting point, the benchmark against which future progress can be assessed or comparisons made.

In IN-HABIT, the baseline study on inclusive health and well-being (IHW) was coordinated and carried out by ISIM. The task is performed with the involvement of partner UREAD, which is responsible for the analysis of data on mental health, and with the involvement of the LCAs working in Riga. The objective of this baseline study on IHW is to identify and describe the starting point of the condition of local target groups in terms of health and well-being. This analysis was based on both qualitative and quantitative key impact indicators that have been pre-identified and co-designed with the involvement of local partners, citizens and local GDEI organisations. The results of the baseline survey are available in Appendix 5.

The baseline study in Riga involved the following:

- One general survey on IHW, which was co-designed by ISIM with the involvement of UREAD and the local research partner BSC. The survey was carried out in September-October 2021;
- One focus group was organised and run in the local language by LCAs with the involvement of seven local inhabitants belonging to the city target groups and living or working in Āgenskalns. Guidelines were provided by ISIM. The focus group took place on 7 October 2021;
- Storytelling was used as an assessment tool in the baseline study. Personal stories from local inhabitants were collected to identify changes introduced by COVID-19 in specific aspects of people's socio-economic well-being and healthy lifestyles. Five stories were collected in Riga. Guidelines were provided by ISIM.

Different channels were employed to distribute the questionnaire and invitation to the focus group. Members of the UAB were asked to distribute the questionnaire. Sociology students at the University of Latvia were engaged to distribute the questionnaire and approach NGOs and neighbourhood associations who subsequently forwarded the link to the online version of the questionnaire to their members. The online version was by far the most popular because it was a convenient way to reach a high number of potential respondents who could then fill in the questionnaire in their own time.

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We noted that the questionnaire sometimes had a negative effect on the respondent, while the focus group was well received. Some senior respondents refused to complete the questionnaire as they said that questions about their physical and mental well-being were no one else's business. Other respondents expressed discomfort and a negative attitude towards the question about their sexual orientation. Finally, some respondents admitted to becoming depressed and uncomfortable after filling in the questionnaire – anecdotal evidence suggests that this may have been the result of having to think about questions that the respondents had hitherto ignored. Response to the focus group, however, was much more positive. People were happy to share their views on topics pertaining to Āgenskalns and life in the neighbourhood.

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4. Co-design of visionary and integrated solutions (VIS): bottom-up participative process

4.1. Co-design workshops

In addition to the co-design workshops aimed at co-creating a list of IHW indicators, **the Riga team has organised three online co-design workshops** aimed primarily at co-articulating a vision for the development of Āgenskalns market with a GDEI perspective. The first two were public events organised in a hybrid format. An expert panel met online (Zoom), and the discussion was broadcast on Facebook and on a screen located in Āgenskalns market to. The third one was attended by members of the UAB.

- 19 August 2021 - Public discussion: E-commerce and food
- 26 August 2021 - Public discussion: Waste as a resource
- 15 February 2022 – UAB meeting & workshop

The workshop on 19 August 2021 was a combination of an expert panel and a public discussion. The panel of experts consisted of representatives of different online businesses who discussed their experience of e-commerce and how COVID-19 has shaped the way different products are purchased and sold online. The panel included

- Ilze Švarcbaha, Kalnciema Quarter;
- Monta Vecozola, manager of KATKEVICH bakery and breakfast café;
- Dāvis Dudelis, owner and manager of Avenei ice cream company;
- Raimonds Selga, co-founder and CTO of SIA "Kalve Coffee";
- Gustavs Gotauts, owner and manager of eCOMHUB.

The expert discussion addressed various e-commerce initiatives, best practices, challenges and future developments. The discussion was followed by a Q&A round where the audience could pose questions. The overall goal was to harvest insights that could be used to improve the online market facility at Āgenskalns market. The panel agreed that, while e-commerce initiatives have obvious potential, a number of organisational and logistical solutions can hamper their development. For instance, trusted delivery services are crucial to ensure timely delivery of

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goods, which is especially important for Āgenskalns market if they decide to sell fresh produce. Distance selling has to inspire confidence in potential customers by ensuring that the quality of products is reliable. Finally, the e-commerce platform itself has to be carefully maintained. Companies that suddenly become popular have frequently encountered the issue that servers cannot handle the heavy traffic that comes with greater interest. These insights will be borne in mind when further developing the online market facility.

Hybrid workshops

The workshop on 26 August 2021 was also a combination of an expert panel and a public discussion. The panel consisted of various experts representing different circular solutions and ways of turning waste into a productive resource or repairing items to prevent them from becoming waste. The panel included

- Ilze Švarcbaha, Kalnciema Quarter;
- Inga Belousa, Green Freedom;
- Ilze Akule, Green Freedom and expert on sustainable fashion;
- Krišjānis Liepa, Repair Café;
- Mairita Lūse, Riga City Council.

The discussion addressed various civil society initiatives in the recycling and management of waste, as well legislative and future developments. The discussion was followed by a Q&A round where the audience could pose questions. The overall goal was to harvest insights that could be used to facilitate the introduction of practices that would minimise waste at Āgenskalns market. While no specific conclusions were reached at the end of the workshop, the discussion

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highlighted various challenges (e.g. inertia) that waste reduction initiatives will likely encounter in Latvia.

The third workshop was also organised online. The intention was to discuss the results of the recent community surveys that addressed all four priority areas. In particular, the core team wanted to consult with the UAB regarding possible ways of reconciling the conflicting visions for the development of Āgenskalns market that were identified in the survey results.

In addition to the workshops, the core team organised two community surveys to gather input and suggestions regarding the development of the market. The surveys indicated that residents of Āgenskalns neighbourhood and (past) users of Āgenskalns market had widely differing expectations from the market. For instance, the idea that, in addition to the provision of food, the market could also function as an inclusive cultural space was received with ambivalence. This is likely due to the popular idea of neighbourhood markets as places where you can buy food, frequently cheaper than in supermarkets. Thus, some respondents indicated that they would like to see a more “traditional” market, rather than a multifunctional hub.

Invitation to participate in the community survey

Divergences of opinion were particularly pronounced in the case of the community kitchen. While the range of activities that will take place in the community kitchen is presently unclear,

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it was apparent from the responses to the survey that some people were uneasy about bringing different social groups together, especially since COVID-19 is still an issue. There were others who believed that the plan to create a community kitchen was salutary, though they would ideally want more details about what exactly will happen there.

The response to the online market facility was likewise ambivalent. While the facility itself was not criticised, some respondents questioned whether an online market version of a neighbourhood market was necessary. It was noted that going to the market and interacting with the vendors is an experience in itself, and ordering food online was not the same. For instance, it was suggested by some that they had no problem using the delivery services provided by supermarkets, but they would prefer to actually go to the market and choose the products themselves.

People were generally positive about the intention to minimise waste. Respondents suggested introducing recycling bins for different types of waste and involving both vendors and customers in a discussion about the importance of re-usable packaging. However, it was also noted that this should not drive the prices up.

The results were discussed with the UAB, and the overall conclusion of the discussion was that additional work will be required to clarify the plan for Āgenskalns market to the different publics that will likely make use of it. There are currently different visions of what Āgenskalns market should be, so the challenge will be to integrate them, while staying true to the initial plans of the developers.

4.2. Bottom-up methods and tools used

The choice of methods in the first year of the IN-HUB has largely been determined by the public health situation in Latvia and the fact that the planned VIS are still at an early stage of development. The choice has been in favour of traditional methods (workshops and surveys) though they have had to be modified to adjust to the circumstances. Specifically, workshops and surveys involved a significant online component, though effort was made to ensure that people who do not use online tools could also participate. Nonetheless, the core team subsequently acknowledged that a more pronounced effort would have to be made in the future to ensure the participation of different groups. The Toolkit will be consulted to achieve this.

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In all cases the topics addressed with the methods described above were tied to the planned VIS. However, their descriptions were intentionally general to encourage discussion without being confined by the practical limitations that the team in charge of Āgenskalns market has to contend with.

The co-design workshops in August 2021 were organised in a hybrid format. The opinion of the core team was that people would be reluctant to attend public events, so the decision was made to prioritise the online component. The discussion between experts would take place on the video conferencing tool Zoom while being simultaneously broadcast on Facebook. However, it was believed that the workshop should be accessible to casual market visitors so the core team decided that it should be simultaneously broadcast on a screen at the market, with a member of the team sitting there to relay any questions to the panel of experts via the Zoom chat. The workshop on 15 February 2021 was not a public event. It was intended as an opportunity to draw on the expertise of the UAB.

In addition to the workshops, the core team organised two community surveys. The first round took place in November-December 2021 (96 responses), the second in January-February 2022 (41 responses). Hard copies were made available at the market (distributed with help from vendors). People could fill in the questionnaire, but they could also scan the QR code placed on the questionnaire and submit their answers online. A link to the online questionnaire was posted on Facebook and Twitter.

4.3. Design for Change (DFC) workshops to promote mindset change

Several meetings were organised with the representatives of DCF Spain to discuss the organisation of mindset change workshops in Latvia. The meetings focused on the dates, the agenda, the best way to approach the participants and various practicalities (e.g. technical equipment for the training). Due to the COVID-19 pandemic situation in Latvia, the workshop dates were changed three times. The initial idea was to organise a face-to-face workshop. However, after considering the situation and restrictions in Latvia, the decision to organise an online workshop was made.

- Initial plan: face-to-face workshop on 15-16 November 2021

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- Revised plan: face-to-face workshop on 26-27 January 2022
- Final plan: online workshop on 2, 9 and 16 February 2022

When the dates were set, the RPR team together with DCF Spain decided that workshop materials should be translated into Latvian - the DFC toolkit, invitation letter, Google registration form.

It was agreed that the Riga planning region team will send out the invitation to potential workshop participants. The participants for the mindset change workshop were recruited via several channels:

- The invitation letter was sent to all Riga city schools, pre-school educational institutions and after-school educational institutions;
- The letter to inform people who work in the formal and informal education sector about the workshop was sent to neighbourhood centres;
- Information about the workshop was sent to different educational organisations: Iespējamā misija (Latvian); University of Latvia, Faculty of Education; Psychology and Art, Latvian Trade Union of Education and Science Employees;
- RPR Facebook account.

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Screenshots from DFC workshops

Nine participants applied to attend the workshop. The participants were asked to sign the imagine and data document before the workshop and create a Gmail account to be able to receive workshop materials.

During three workshop days, the participants had the opportunity to learn the design for change method, which is structured in five steps: the identification of a challenge, the generation of ideas, the action, the reflection and the communication of the projects. Different learning methods were used during the workshop - discussion in groups or pairs, presentations, games etc.

Initial evaluation was done on the final day of the workshop and in-depth evaluation was made via e-mail after the workshop. After the workshop, a letter thanking participants for their attendance for attendance together with the workshop materials and certificate were sent. A press release was created and published on the RPR home page about the workshop and results.

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5. City-specific VIS to boost IHW

5.1. Planned hard and soft solutions

The planned VIS were based on the recognition that Āgenskalns market is an important public space in the neighbourhood, and it has a significant impact on the well-being of the local community. The market has historically been the heart of Āgenskalns neighbourhood where people purchased food and gathered together.

Site visit on 1 February 2022

The initial plans for Āgenskalns market involved both hard (infrastructural) and soft (practices, events) solutions. In particular, the plan was to concentrate on: (i) improvements to the physical public infrastructure in and around the territory of Āgenskalns market in Riga, and (ii) the promotion of food related educational and consumption practices. While some key components of the solutions (spaces to be renovated, main infrastructural innovations and functions) had been clearly defined at the outset (e.g. equipment for the community kitchen), it was believed that **many elements of the transformation plan would be co-designed with local stakeholders** to ensure that a variety of perspectives would have a chance to shape the development of Āgenskalns market.

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The Riga IN-HUB has made a consistent effort to ensure that specific (vulnerable and less represented) groups of the population are involved in market activities and the elaboration of the VIS. Vulnerability is sometimes socially invisible. Therefore, we focus on groups which are not “the usual suspects” and aim to develop concrete strategies for their involvement. This will remain an important part of our work throughout the project, and we will try to accommodate the specific needs of ethnic minorities, young and single parents, people who live alone, senior citizens, people with disabilities, and other groups.

Several integrated solutions were initially proposed to be co-developed with the direct involvement of local residents, businesses, NGOs, farmers and educational institutions.

- Transformation of a public square and related traffic junctions next to Āgenskalns market into a new, easily accessible and green urban square to encourage the use of bicycles and healthy mobility practices.
- New green zones, sports facilities and art corners will be co-deployed in collaboration with local artists, sports associations and enterprises.
- Interactive events for children and parents about healthy nutrition and sustainable diets.
- Educational courses for urban gardeners in collaboration with specialists of the Botanical Garden of University of Latvia and other partners.
- Behavioural games, digital guidance and information provided via the INHABIT-APP to support healthy diets, sustainable food production/consumption and recycling practices as well as physical activity and sports (walking and cycling) in the neighbourhood.
- Novel food chain arrangements that bring together farmers, small scale processors, food artisans, craftsmen and women, catering businesses and consumers in order to shorten supply chains and promote healthy food habits (ongoing).
- Culinary events, vocational training and educational activities in the community kitchen, with the involvement of children, the elderly and other vulnerable groups (ethnic minorities, persons with disabilities), thereby contributing to social cohesion and delivering a fair and equitable distribution of benefits.
- New collection and re-use practices for food close to its expiration date in collaboration with market vendors.

These activities are still on the agenda and more specific action plans will be developed as a result of consultations in the local IN-HUB. However, the practical investment, development and

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public debates that have unfolded around Āgenskalns market in 2020 and 2021 have profiled **four key directions of work** for the coming years, which have been fleshed out via the top-down and bottom-up processes described in Section 4.

5.2. Co-designed VIS

While creating the vision for the revitalisation process in Āgenskalns market and the direction that IN-HABIT would take in Riga, we took into consideration the local context and the needs of the local community. We explored different options through community surveys and public workshops with the residents of the neighbourhood. The overall vision that the Riga team has gravitated towards was that Āgenskalns market needs to be a multifunctional, open, and inclusive public space. It will primarily function as a market with a focus on making locally sourced food more easily accessible. However, it will also provide cultural and educational opportunities, thus acting as a kind of community or cultural centre in the neighbourhood. By taking this approach, the team envisioned several ways in which the market can have an impact on the neighbourhood and the community, such as inclusive health, environmental awareness, educational and cultural opportunities, economic growth, and innovative solutions through interdisciplinary cooperation.

This approach has coalesced into four main directions of work, which were developed around food and its diverse functions in the neighbourhood and the community.

1. Transformation of the outdoor marketplace
2. Community kitchen
3. Minimisation of waste at the market
4. Online food purchasing system

(1) The KQ team has long-term experience in placemaking by restoring and preserving previously undervalued cultural heritage in an inclusive way to make it available to different social groups. Based on the input obtained from workshops and community surveys, the KQ team will seek to renovate and transform the market territory and make it appealing and accessible to different people and their needs, taking into consideration the needs of young people, children, seniors, mothers, people with disabilities, foreigners etc. Crucially, this VIS will have an important role in meeting local expectations, defining the identity of the market and its role in the neighbourhood.

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(2) Throughout the years of operating the market in Kalnciema Quarter, the KQ team recognised that food is a medium that can create connections between people and open up discussions on traditional and regional heritage, health, and well-being. Therefore, taking into consideration the vision of Āgenskalns market as a space of inclusion and interaction, the team developed the idea of creating the first community kitchen in Riga to foster an open community in the neighbourhood and potentially create a place for marginalised groups. This, however, will require the Riga team to define and explain the purpose of the community kitchen to visitors as this is a new concept in Latvia (novelty confirmed via community surveys).

(3) The theme of sustainability and environmentally conscious consumer behaviour has always been important in the work of KQ. The KQ team is cognisant of the role of food in environmental processes and the impact of the market on it as an epicentre of consumption and food waste. The KQ team will draw upon existing examples of multifunctional markets and seek to adapt them in Āgenskalns market to create an innovative approach and sustainable system that also provides educational opportunities for the local community. This VIS, however, will require cooperation from vendors and customers in the implementation of waste minimisation policies.

(4) KQ recognises the importance of facilities that allow it to reach a wider audience through digital solutions and optimise the availability of local food in different regions. Therefore, the team seeks to create and improve upon the first online market facility for a neighbourhood market in Latvia to support local farmers and producers by offering them a new platform for distributing their food as well as improving access to healthy food at an affordable price.

All four are examples of incremental innovation as they are not radical departures from available solutions and build upon existing examples found both locally and abroad. Nonetheless, they are contextually novel and will seek to (i) introduce changes in the way people socialise at the market, (ii) create opportunities for different groups to bond over food and (iii) encourage healthy and more sustainable consumption practices. With the exception of the fourth direction (online market), **a GDEI perspective is implicit in our work** as the needs of vulnerable and at-risk-of-exclusion groups have been and will continue to be considered.

It should be noted that COVID-19 caused a significant delay in fully opening Āgenskalns market. Consequently, three of the VIS are currently only in the planning stages and will take a

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more definite shape when the market pavilion will be opened for business. This means that they are currently still in the visioning stage.

5.3. Co-deployment and co-management of VIS

Solution #1	Transformation of the outdoor marketplace
Short description	Restoration of the area outside the market pavilion into a dynamic and inclusive multifunctional space for social gatherings that combines food provision with cultural and educational opportunities.
Users	Local residents, people from other parts of Riga and Latvia, vendors, NGOs, research and educational organisations, tourists
Stakeholders consulted	Local residents, NGOs, small businesses, Riga City Council, neighbourhood associations, architects
Co-design format	Co-design workshops, community surveys and email correspondence
Key issues to be resolved prior to co-deployment	Alignment and integration of (i) competing visions of the marketplace expressed by stakeholders and (ii) conflicting needs and interests of car drivers and other road users in and around the market.
Co-deployment	During consultations with the UAB and by networking with other public and private actors a new idea was developed for cooperation with the state-owned enterprise <i>Latvijas Valsts meži</i> (Latvian State Forests) and Bulduri Horticultural College to improve the outdoor marketplace by planting trees and establishing a green area. A preliminary agreement has been reached that Latvian State Forests will donate the planting material and the students of Bulduri Horticultural College would take part in maintaining the plants.

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	Thereby, this activity would result in a hard solution and include young people in urban place-shaping (a soft solution). Renovation and construction work will be done by a private company hired by KQ. Layout and organisation will be negotiated with vendors and the UAB.
Co-management	The primary actor is KQ, but the outdoor marketplace (both in form and in function) is envisaged as dynamically changing in response to demand.
Implementation timeline	M19-24 will be devoted to organising different events with the aim of establishing the outdoor area as a key social and cultural venue in the neighbourhood. This will include building a makeshift community stage for cultural events and making use of the <i>Siltumnīca</i> (a greenhouse) for public discussions. Thematically relevant events will cover community involvement in the greening of the outdoor area, sustainable diets, safe and environmentally friendly mobility practices (all M22). The plan is also to host the neighbourhood festival (M23), a recycling and repair workshop and a young people’s festival (M24) Subsequent activities will include both cultural events and the implementation of hard solutions, further refined via co-creation activities in the autumn of 2022.

Solution #2	Community kitchen
Short description	A dedicated area on the first floor of the market pavilion equipped with the necessary appliances to host community cooking and co-creation events targeted at different audiences.

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Users	Local residents, tourists, students, children, educators (e.g. nutrition specialists), professional cooks
Stakeholders consulted	Local residents, NGOs, small businesses, Riga City Council, neighbourhood associations, architects, nutrition specialists
Co-design format	Co-design workshops, community surveys and email correspondence, consultations with nutrition specialists
Key issues to be resolved prior to co-deployment	(i) Clarification of the purpose of the community kitchen to potential users, (ii) ensuring health and safety standards for cooking in public spaces, (iii) finalisation of procurement procedure for the necessary equipment.
Co-deployment	Organisation and focus will be negotiated with the UAB and potential users. During the site visit and discussion among members of the UAB, architects, market managers and the core team additional practical ideas about the uses of the community kitchen were proposed. First, the stakeholders proposed to make the kitchen open to various publics. Second, the kitchen premises on the second floor would be located next to a stage where various cultural activities and performances will take place. Third, KQ has been in contact with nutrition specialists from the nearby Riga Stradins University who have agreed to organise and run classes on healthy nutrition and cooking for children. Fourth, IN-HUB members proposed to rename the community kitchen a 'co-creation kitchen' to emphasise its open nature and the various creative activities that will be organised there. Installation of the necessary equipment will be done by a private company hired by KQ.
Co-management	The primary actor is KQ. The range of events will be planned in cooperation with local NGOs, scientific organisations and public institutions to ensure that a wide range of people (including those at risk of discrimination) are involved in events organised in the community kitchen.

Implementation timeline	M19-24 will be devoted to finalising the procurement procedure to initiate the purchase and installation of the relevant equipment. Any delays in the procurement process (hard solutions) will require the team to postpone all soft solutions that depend on the availability of the necessary equipment. In such a scenario, the area will be temporarily repurposed.
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Solution #3	Minimisation of waste at the market
Short description	Implementation of policies at the market that nudge vendors and customers to engage in environmentally sustainable consumption practices. This will involve facilities for recycling, guidelines for buying and selling goods using reusable packaging, and educational events aimed at teaching visitors to consume responsibly and create less waste.
Users	Local residents, environmental NGOs, small businesses, Riga City Council, neighbourhood associations
Stakeholders consulted	NGOs, experts on recycling, vendors, neighbourhood associations
Co-design format	Co-design workshops, community surveys, email correspondence, consultations with representatives of the Zero Waste movement and Riga City Council
Issues to be resolved prior to co-deployment	Clear guidelines regarding the use of reusable packaging for vendors, installation of recycling infrastructure
Co-deployment	Various specific directions of work have been considered in IN-HUB discussions: (i) to set up an exchange point for used goods, (ii) to provide information and incentives for market vendors to introduce re-usable and sustainable packaging; (iii) to open a repair shop at the market. While guidelines will be prepared by KQ in consultation with the UAB, the implementation of these policies will depend on successful cooperation with businesses, vendors and customers.

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Co-management	The KQ team will monitor the implementation of waste minimisation policies at Āgenskalns market.
Implementation timeline	New waste collection and sorting services will be made available to vendors after the opening of the market (M21). Subsequently, work on the preparation of waste minimisation guidelines in consultation with Zero Waste Latvia, the UAB and vendors will commence, based on an analysis of the volume and kinds of waste generated at the market. This work will feed into the creation of an autonomous waste management system at the market.

Solution #4	Online food purchasing system
Short description	An online sales facility for ordering products sold at the market for pickup and delivery, with an emphasis on locally sourced food with high nutritional content.
Users	No specific profile
Stakeholders consulted	Local residents, neighbourhood association, e-commerce experts, online food businesses
Co-design format	Co-design workshops, community surveys and email correspondence, consultations with e-commerce experts
Issues to be resolved prior to co-deployment	Solution has been deployed, but payment and pickup facilities will continue to be refined as these have been identified as problem areas in the community survey. Other suggestions from the UAB relate to the provision of ready-made food baskets, which have been tailored to specific demographic and dietary groups to also ensure dietary inclusivity.
Co-deployment	The KQ team deployed the solution in 2020 in response to COVID-19 restrictions in collaboration with several vendors
Co-management	Managed by the KQ team

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Implementation timeline	The online sales facility will be revised after the opening of the main market pavilion (M21) to accommodate new vendors. The physical collection point will be improved, frequency of deliveries will be increased, and the webpage will be streamlined to make ordering products online more convenient.
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6. Emerging lessons and recommendations

6.1. Challenges and achievements in the organization and development of the IN-HUB and PPPPs schemes

The establishment of the Riga IN-HUB and introduction of the PPPP principle has been successful. The core team, together with the UAB, has been successful in establishing links with Āgenskalns neighbourhood community members and businesses, as well as with private and public partners in Riga. This has happened due to regular communication and consistent efforts to involve various actors in project activities. The IN-HUB in Riga has gained publicity at the neighbourhood and city levels. Various media channels have been used to achieve this. In addition, purposeful networking with public and private actors, educational, governance and business organisations has helped to find new potential partners for designing and implementing the planned VIS.

The first year of the Riga IN-HUB has provided a solid foundation in terms of structure, functions, forms of work and pathways towards the expected health and well-being impacts. The Riga IN-HUB is inspired by the new European urban agenda which emphasises an integrated approach to human-centred cities. The Riga IN-HUB mobilises relatively undervalued resources, such as food in relation to culture and social activities, for a particular urban development project – the transformation of a historical marketplace, Āgenskalns market, in Riga into an innovative and multifunctional food hub. The Riga IN-HUB, together with a private company, stands as one of the main driving forces towards conversion of a historical market into a multifunctional food hub which combines a diverse set of economic, cultural, sports, educational and ecological activities and has a strong focus on the health and wellbeing of local residents. In doing so the Riga IN-HUB works closely with market managers, private investors, other businesses, architects, urban planners, research organisations and neighbourhood communities to openly design and develop solutions that meet the needs of various publics.

The composition of the Riga IN-HUB has been enriched through participatory activities and the pathways towards achieving the desired impact have become clearer. We observe that participatory activities facilitated by the Riga IN-HUB have ensured community engagement in the co-creation and co-ownership of an urban marketplace and generated further impact

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pathways in terms of innovation, inclusion, governance, and wellbeing. The figure below presents the emerging impact pathways facilitated by the IN-HUB.

Emerging impact pathways facilitated by the IN-HUB

The Riga team has encountered several practical obstacles in achieving its objectives, mainly due to the public health situation. The COVID-19 pandemic has had a direct influence on the Riga IN-HUB because it has postponed the practical implementation of VIS in Āgenskalns market. Consequently, the market has remained a mental construct, rather than an actual physical place, which likely influenced co-creation activities. The context of the pandemic was discouraging in general, and people have indicated on several occasions that they would prefer to avoid gatherings, even when this was permitted (e.g. the focus group discussion almost had to be postponed due to several last-day cancellations). To overcome these obstacles, the team has been adjusting its communication and outreach activities (e.g. diversification of communication channels, hybrid events, translation of project materials). While the results have generally been satisfactory, the team expects faster progress once the restrictions have been lifted, and people are no longer hesitant to attend public gatherings.

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These obstacles notwithstanding, the IN-HUB has been established and is able to attract interest from people and organisations who are invested in the future of Āgenskalns market. Furthermore, experimentation with hybrid methods of involving different stakeholders will likely remain important so the experience the team has accumulated over the first year will undoubtedly be useful. Finally, the establishment of the IN-HUB and its first year of operation has also helped to gain a better understanding of the various institutional silos and gaps in urban development, which will be crucial in designing activities and actions to address them.

6.2. Challenges and achievements in combining bottom-up and top-down co-design, mindset change, and social innovations

IN-HUB activities have aimed to find the right balance between top-down and bottom-approaches. In the initial phase, the Riga IN-HUB employed a predominantly top-down approach, and activities were mostly initiated and implemented by the core team. When the UAB was established and became operational, and the various co-design activities were organised (workshops, consultations, surveys, interviews, feedbacks, etc.), the perspective of local residents became more prominent in the placemaking process.

We have noted that participants have (sometimes wildly) different and conflicting opinions and visions about the desirable transformations and social innovations that are necessary in Riga. While involvement in the project's activities stimulates their participation in visioning future of the neighbourhood, only a few of the proposed solutions can be brought to life. This has been explicitly addressed in meetings with the UAB. Nonetheless, awareness of these differences is immensely important, and the various methods that we have employed in co-design processes have provided invaluable insight.

The Riga IN-HUB is engaged in placemaking at multiple scales. As a physical place, Āgenskalns market occupies a relatively small area. However, its relative importance in terms of economic and social activity and as an urban landmark extends beyond the locality. The ideas, capital and support for its development into a creative and multifunctional food hub are derived and mobilised through networks and relationships that extend across various scales: the neighbourhood, Riga as a whole, the Greater Riga Region and beyond. Whereas the hard solutions are tied to a specific physical space, the soft solutions and their impacts tend to reach a much wider range of people who benefit from activities aimed at increasing IHW.

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There is different progress and dynamics at the project level and the local level. On some occasions, local partners were ready to proceed with the activities, but there were procedures that had to be followed at the project level, and vice versa – in some cases the situation in the cities precluded them from doing things the way the transversal partners would have liked.

6.3. Challenges and achievements in ensuring the GDEI perspective

One of the key challenges remains the limited involvement of some target groups, such as elderly people and ethnic minorities. Some of this can be explained by the restrictions imposed due to the spread of COVID-19 - elderly people are generally less skilled or willing to use digital communication channels and tools, so they were unable to participate. However, the limited involvement of ethnic minorities is harder to explain and will need to be addressed. In some cases, there were few entry points to get in touch with some groups because of their limited public visibility and a lack of (or unresponsive) organisations. This will be addressed in subsequent work that will aim to develop concrete strategies for engaging the relevant groups in a more targeted manner, thus ensuring their participation and contribution to the overall goals of the Riga pilot.

6.4. Assessment of and reflection on the Toolkit: methods and tools used in the co-design, co-deployment, and co-management of VIS

The team has occasionally noted that the overall purpose and value added of some activities is not sufficiently clear, which has required a creative re-interpretation of the description of these activities to make sure that people are willing to attend. It is not clear whether this is due to cultural differences. Furthermore, it is likely that the IN-HUB will encounter issues in the co-deployment and co-management stages and will require assistance from transversal partners to address them.

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6.5. Emerging recommendations: city-specific, comparative among the cities, general

- It is important to ground IN-HUB work in the city context in terms of the wellbeing situation, needs of the population and the agenda implicit in the city's development plans and policies.
- It is equally important to build on the development legacy, relevant previous and ongoing development projects and initiatives and create synergies with them to maximise the relevance and impact of the IN-HUB.
- The IN-HUB is an open structure meant to stimulate and drive the process of co-creation. It requires continuous effort in terms of mobilisation, facilitation, monitoring and evaluation to make it effective.
- The desired effect and impact of the IN-HUB in terms of improved health and wellbeing depends on its enlargement according to the principles of PPPP. This can be achieved by purposeful networking.
- The dynamic co-design and co-deployment of sustainable hard and soft solutions for the health and wellbeing of citizens are dependent on the skilful management of the IN-HUB.

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Appendixes

Appendix 1. Stakeholder mapping

Different stakeholders identified

- NGOs representing people with disabilities (e.g. Apeirons)
- NGOs representing senior citizens

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- Cultural organisations: musical schools in the neighbourhood, theatres, museums, private cultural initiatives and artists.
- Environmental organisations (e.g. Zaļā brīvība [Green Freedom]), zero waste movement.
- NGOs representing minorities (e.g. Mozaīka)
- Urban policy and city planning organisations and administrative units: Alija Turlaja – an elected deputy of Riga city council, city planners, architects, the Riga City Development Department, experts from Strategic Planning division at the City Council.
- Neighbourhood associations: Primarily Āgenskalns neighbourhood association, but other neighbourhood associations (e.g. Jugla) have expressed an interest in learning from IN-HABIT.
- The residents of Āgenskalns neighbourhood
- Students: three university campuses are located near Āgenskalns market and a high number of students live in the surrounding area.
- State institutions: e.g. the Ministry of Culture, in particular, experts on creative industries who might be interested in Āgenskalns market as a model incubator for creative industries.
- Media: e.g. the National TV programme TE, magazine IR which might be approached with the idea to release a special issue on Āgenskalns market.
- Entrepreneurs: cafes, farmers, designers, real estate developers, restoration companies active in the neighbourhood.

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Appendix 2. Supplementary documents for the User Advisory Board

Memorandum of cooperation (in Latvian)

SADARBĪBAS MEMORANDS

Rīgā

2021. gada __. _____

Eiropas Savienības pētniecības un inovācijas ietvarprogrammas „Horizonts 2020” projekta “Veselīgas un iekļaujošas pilsētas” (IN-HABIT – Inclusive health and well-being in small and medium sized cities) (turpmāk -Projekts) ietvaros, kur no vienas puses projekta partneri:

- Rīgas plānošanas reģions, Administrācijas vadītāja p.i. Rūdolfa Cimdiņa personā,
- Baltic Studies Centre, vadošā pētnieka Tāļa Tisenkopfa personā
- SIA “BC manufaktūra” projektu vadītājas Unas Meibergas personā,

un no otras puses:

Organizācijas nosaukums, amats Vārds Uzvārds personā,

noslēdz šo sadarbības memorandu (turpmāk – Memorands) par savstarpējo sadarbību.

1. Memoranda mērķis

Memoranda mērķis ir veicināt Pušu sadarbību **Konsultatīvās padomes (turpmāk – Padome) ietvaros**, lai identificētu sadarbības formu reģionālā, nacionālā un Eiropas līmenī izveidotu daudzfunkcionālu pārtikas centru ilgtspējīgi ražotai vietējai pārtikai – Āgenskalna tirgū.

2. Mērķa īstenošana

- 2.1. Lai sekmētu Memorandā noteiktā mērķa sasniegšanu, Puses īsteno savas tiesības un pienākumus saskaņā ar Padomes nolikumā noteikto.
- 2.2. Puses Padomes darbā ievēro atklātību, nodrošina informācijas pieejamību, pauž savus viedokļus, sekmē nepieciešamo sadarbības mehānisma izstrādi, sagatavo priekšlikumus identificētā sadarbības modeļa sasniegšanai.
- 2.3. Puses sekmē informācijas un zināšanu apmaiņu to organizāciju/ valsts pārvaldes iestāžu starpā, kuru darbības saistās ar atvērtas un iekļaujošas kopienas telpas izveidi Āgenskalna tirgū un apkaimē.

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- 2.4. Puses atbalsta atbilstošas Padomes nolikumā ietvertajiem mērķiem Pušu aktivitātes Āgenskalna tirgū un apkaimē.
- 2.5. Puses savas kompetences ietvaros nodrošina daudzlīmeņu komunikāciju un sadarbību, lai sekmētu politisko atbalstu veselīgu un iekļaujošu kopienu popularizēšanā Āgenskalna apkaimē.

3. Projekta partneru saistības

- 3.1. Atbilstoši nosprausto "IN-HABIT" projektā noteikto mērķu sasniegšanai un paredzētajam finansējumam, nodrošina projekta materiālus, kā arī sniedz informāciju par "IN-HABIT" projekta rezultātiem.
- 3.2. Organizē Padomes sanāksmes par atvērtas un iekļaujošas kopienas telpas izveides tēmu Āgenskalna apkaimē.

4. Padomes locekļa saistības

- 4.1. Aņņemas darboties Padomē ne mazāk kā vienu gadu no Memoranda noslēgšanas dienas. Ja līdz Memoranda beigu termiņam ir palicis mazāk kā viens gads, šajā gadījumā aņņemas darboties Padomē uz atlikušo laiku.
- 4.2. Veicināt Padomes nolikumā noteikto mērķu un uzdevumu sasniegšanu, īstēnot paredzētās tiesības un ievērot Padomes darba organizāciju.
- 4.3. Piedalīties projekta "IN-HABIT" aktivitātēs, kas saistītas ar atvērtas un iekļaujošas kopienas telpas izveides tēmu Āgenskalna apkaimē: sanāksmēs, diskusijās, pasākumos, vebināros, kā arī pēc izvēles projekta aktivitātēs.
- 4.4. Sadarboties ar citiem Padomes pārstāvjiem, t.sk. apmainoties ar informāciju un zināšanām par atvērtas un iekļaujošas kopienas telpas izveides tēmu.

5. Atbildība, pārstāvība, izbeigšana un grozījumi

- 5.1. Atbildība: Puses ir atbildīgas par šajā Memorandā noteikto saistību izpildi. Puses nav atbildīgas par otras Puses saistību neizpildi.
- 5.2. Pārstāvniecība: Pusēm nav tiesību pārstāvēt kādu citu Padomes locekli un paust tā viedokli trešajai personai, tajā skaitā sociālajiem medijiem, preseī.
- 5.3. Izbeigšana: Pēc 4.1. punktā noteiktā termiņa beigām, Pusēm ir tiesības atkāpties no Memoranda jebkurā laikā.
- 5.4. Grozījumi: Grozījumi šajā Memorandā var tikt izdarīti rakstiski, Pusēm abpusēji vienojoties.

6. Pušu kontaktpersonas un pilnvarotie pārstāvji Padomē

- 6.1. Rīgas plānošanas reģions: "IN-HABIT" projekta koordinatore Aija Zučika.
- 6.2. Baltic Studies Centre: Vadošais pētnieks Tālis Tisenkopfs

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6.3. SIA "BC manufaktūra": projektu vadītāja Una Meiberga

7. PERSONU DATU AIZSARDZĪBA

- 7.1. Padomes sēdē "INHABIT" projekta aktivitāšu publicitātes nodrošināšanai vai Padomes mērķu sasniegšanai, var tikt veikta fotofiksācija un/vai filmēšana un/vai tiešraides nodrošināšana ar mērķi atspoguļot sadarbības un aktivitāšu gaitu vai to rezultātus, līdz ar to Padomes locekļa darbs var kļūt sabiedrībā atpazīstams.
- 7.2. Puses, ar Memoranda parakstīšanu, izvirzot vai nozīmējot darbam pārstāvi Padomē (Memoranda 6. nodaļa), apliecina, ka Padomes loceklis ir piekritis sava vizuāla attēla publiskošanai, identificējot ar vārdu un uzvārdu, kā arī kā attiecīgā apkaimes iedzīvotāju vai interešu grupas pārstāvi, projekta "INHABIT" un Padomes sociālajos tīklos (facebook, Instagram un tml.), masu mediju tīmekļa vietnēs, portālos, laikrakstos u.c. "INHABIT" projekta partneru veiktās fotofiksācijas vai audiovizuālie materiāli glabāsies 10 (desmit) gadus pēc Projekta īstenošanas pabeigšanas. Pēc termiņa beigām dati neatgriezeniski tiks dzēsti.
- 7.3. Padomes loceklim ir tiesības jebkurā laikā atsaukt 7.2. punktā sniegto piekrišanu, un lūgt dzēst savus attēlu un informāciju par sevi projekta "INHABIT" un Padomes publicitātes materiālos, tīmekļa vietnēs un tml, norādot attēla saiti. Projekta "INHABIT" partneris izvērtēs katru gadījumu un iespēju robežās centīsies ievērot Padomes locekļa vēlmes un tiesības, taču projekta "INHABIT" partnerim nav pienākuma dzēst attēlus, kuros nav iespējams tieši identificēt datu subjektu vai arī attēla un informācijas publiskošana ir neatgriezeniska, piemēram bukleti, brošūras, laikraksti un tml.
- 7.4. Puses ir tiesīgas Memoranda 6. nodaļā norādītos publiski izpaust, ievietot tīmekļa vietnēs, sociālajos tīklos un tml.

8. Noslēguma jautājumi

- 8.1. Memorands stājas spēkā nākamajā dienā pēc tā parakstīšanas un ir spēkā līdz 2025. gada 1. septembrim.
- 8.2. Visus jautājumus un domstarpības, kas saistītas ar Memoranda izpildi, Puses risina sarunu ceļā.
- 8.3. Memorands sagatavots uz četrām lapām, divos eksemplāros ar vienādu juridisko spēku, pa vienam eksemplāram katrai Pusei.

Rīgas plānošanas reģions

Rūdolfš Cimdiņš

Administrācijas vadītāja p.i.

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Baltic Studie Centre

Tālis Tisenkofs

Vadošais pētnieks

SIA "BC manufaktūra"

Una Meibergas

Projektu vadītāja

Padomes loceklis

Statutes of the User Advisory Board (in Latvian)

"IN-HABIT: Veselīgas un iekļaujošas pilsētas" Eiropas Savienības pētniecības un inovāciju atbalsta programmas "Apvārsnis 2020" projekta KONSULTATĪVĀS PADOMES NOLIKUMS"

1. Vispārīgie jautājumi

- 1.1. Nolikums nosaka projekta IN-HABIT konsultatīvā padomes (turpmāk tekstā - Padome) struktūru, izveidošanas kārtību, uzdevumus, pienākumus, tiesības un atbildību.
- 1.2. Padome ir konsultatīva institūcija, kura tiek izveidota pēc IN-HABIT projekta īstenotāju iniciatīvas ar mērķi izveidot daudzfunkcionālu pārtikas centru ilgtspējīgi ražotai vietējai pārtikai vietējā – Āgenskalna tirgus teritorijā.
- 1.3. Padomi veido organizāciju un institūciju pārstāvji, kā arī Rīgas iedzīvotāji, kuri ir gatavi iesaistīties Āgenskalna apkaimes attīstības plānošanā un projektu realizēšanā un vēlams pārstāv arī citu iedzīvotāju intereses Rīgas pilsētā un darbojas uz brīvprātības principiem, kā arī kalpo kā sabiedriskās domas veidošanas instruments.
- 1.4. Padomes darbu koordinēšanu nodrošina IN-HABIT projekta vadības grupa (turpmāk tekstā - Komanda).

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2. Padomes darbības mērķi un uzdevumi

- 2.1. Padomes darbības mērķis ir sekmēt projektā plānoto aktivitāšu īstenošanu iekļaujot pēc iespējas vairāk dažādas sabiedrības grupas un aktivizēt dialogu starp pašvaldību, valsts institūcijām, nevalstiskajām organizācijām, vietējiem uzņēmējiem un iedzīvotājiem, tādējādi, veicinot viedokļu apmaiņu un tādu lēmumu pieņemšanu, kuru mērķis ir Āgenskalnā izveidot daudzfunkcionālu pārtikas centru ilgtspējīgi ražotai vietējai pārtikai vietējā tirgus teritorijā.
- 2.2. Padomes darbība ir vērsta uz konsultatīvo atbalstu, ierosinājumu un priekšlikumu sagatavošanu un iesniegšanu Komandai projekta sasniedzamo mērķu īstenošanai.
- 2.3. Padomes uzdevumi:
 - 2.3.1. paust viedokli par projektā plānotajām aktivitātēm un to ietekmi uz apkaimes attīstību;
 - 2.3.2. noskaidrot apkaimes iedzīvotāju viedokli par dažādiem jautājumiem un sagatavot priekšlikumus to risināšanai;
 - 2.3.3. līdzdarboties projekta pozitīva tēla veidošanas pasākumos;
 - 2.3.4. apzināt un apkopot ar projektu sasniedzamajiem mērķiem saistītās aktuālās problēmas un iespēju robežās sniegt priekšlikumus to risināšanai;

3. Padomes tiesības

- 3.1. Padomei ir tiesības:
 - 3.1.1. organizēt sanāksmes un izbraukuma sēdes;
 - 3.1.2. saņemt no Komandas informāciju par plānotajām iecerēm un risināmajiem jautājumiem;
 - 3.1.3. sadarboties ar institūcijām un organizācijām citos Latvijas novados, kā arī ārvalstīs;
 - 3.1.4. pēc savas iniciatīvas sniegt ierosinājumus par apkaimes attīstībai aktuāliem jautājumiem.

4. Padomes izveide, sastāvs un darba organizācija

- 4.1. Padome sastāv no 14 locekļiem.
- 4.2. Padomes sēde var notikt, ja tajā piedalās vairāk kā puse Padomes locekļu.
- 4.3. Padomes locekļus ieceļ ar Komandas lēmumu.
- 4.4. Par padomes locekli var kļūt jebkurš interesents, kurš ir iesniedzis savu motivācijas vēstuli un veicis pārrunas ar Komandu.
- 4.5. Padomei ir no Komandas vidus iecelts priekšsēdētājs, kura kompetence ir saistīta ar Padomes darba organizēšanu.
- 4.6. Padomes darbu organizē un vada Padomes priekšsēdētājs, viņa prombūtnes laikā – priekšsēdētāja vietnieks.
- 4.7. Padomes lēmumiem ir rekomendējošs raksturs un tie tiek pieņemti, Padomes locekļiem balsojot ar balsu vairākumu. Padomes gala lēmumus pieņem 3 Komandas pārstāvji.
- 4.8. Padomes priekšsēdētājs sasauc Padomes sēdes pēc nepieciešamības, bet ne retāk kā 2 reizes gadā. Paziņojums par Padomes sēdes norises laiku, vietu un darba kārtību ne vēlāk kā trīs dienas pirms sēdes tiks izsūtīts uz padomes locekļu norādītajiem e-pastiem.
- 4.9. Lai nodrošinātu visu ieinteresēto pušu līdzdalību jautājumu apspriešanā, uz Padomes sēdi var tikt aicināti arī dažādu sabiedrisko organizāciju, uzņēmumu, iestāžu vai pašvaldības pārstāvji, kas pārstāv noteiktu sabiedrības grupu intereses.
- 4.10. Padomes sēdes tiek protokolētas.

4.11. Padomes lietvedības kārtošanu (sēdes protokolēšanu, citu dokumentu izstrādāšanu un glabāšanu) nodrošina Komandas pārstāvji.

5. Padomes darbības laiks un pārtraukšana

5.1. Padome tiek izveidota uz projekta realizācijas laiku – 01.03.2021.-31.12.2025., kas nepieciešamības gadījumā var tikt pagarināts.

5.2. Nepieciešamības gadījumā jebkuru Padomes locekli no pienākumu pildīšanas var atbrīvot ar Komandas lēmumu.

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Appendix 3. City-specific IHW indicators

IHW indicators: social well-being

Sub-dimension	Expected change (P=partners' view / C=citizens' view)	Indicator	Description
Perception of security	Increased sense of safety (C)	sense of safety at night	Persons who feel safe walking at night in the city (Quantitative/Self reported/Key Impact Indicator)
		Fear of road accidents	Persons who express fear to be victim of road accidents when walking or cycling in the street of their neighborhood (Quantitative/Self reported/Key Impact Indicator)
		sense of safety in green areas	Persons who feel safe to walk in the public green areas of their neighborhood (Quantitative/Self reported/Key Impact Indicator)
		perception of crime, violence or vandalism in the living area	Average level of crime, violence and vandalism in the neighborhood perceived by persons on a range from 1-10 (Quantitative/Self reported/Key Impact Indicator)
Social Inclusion	Increased social relations in public spaces (P; C)	Contact with others in public spaces	Persons who get together with friends and relatives in public spaces once a week (Quantitative/Self reported/Key Impact Indicator)

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		Domestic Isolation	Persons who spend the majority of their time alone at home (Qualitative/self reported/Key impact indicator)
	Improved sense of inclusion (P; C)	Sense of inclusion	persons who feel to be part of the community (Quantitative and qualitative/Self reported/Key Impact Indicator)
	Improved social engagement (P)	Social engagement 1	persons who declare to participate in voluntary activities (social, cultural, educational, religious) (Quantitative/Self reported/Key Impact Indicator)
		Social engagement 2	persons who are satisfied with their level of involvement in the local community life Qualitative/Self Reported/Key Impact Indicator
		Social engagement 3	People who are committed to take care of public spaces and green areas in their neighborhood (Qualitative/Self Reported/Key Impact Indicator)
	Increased change-making attitude (P)	Change-making attitude	persons who believe they can change the reality of their neighborhood (social situation, beauty/attractiveness of the space, economic situation)
Equality	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Sense of being treated equally	Persons who feel they are treated with less courtesy and respect than others (or other groups) (Qualitative/Self reported/Context indicator)

	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Access to internet from home	Persons who have access to internet from home (Quantitative/Self reported/Context Indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Obstacles for the access to culture and leisure	Persons who think to have economic, time, family, mobility, cognitive, cultural obstacles in the access to culture and leisure opportunities in their City/neighborhood (Quantitative and qualitative/Self reported /context Indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Obstacles for the access to training opportunities	Persons who think to have economic, time, family, mobility, cognitive, linguistic/cultural, social obstacles in the access to training opportunities in their city (qualitative and quantitative/Self reported /context Indicator)
Discrimination	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Perception of discrimination in society	Persons who believe that minority groups are considered dangerous/dishonest/ criminals/ unreliable/ bad neighbours by local citizens (qualitative/Self reported /context Indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Perceived personal condition of discrimination	Persons who can describe themselves as being a member of a group that is discriminated against in their country. (qualitative/Self reported /context Indicator)
Spatial well-being	Improved accessibility of local resources (P; C)	Accessibility of local resources	Persons who think in their neighborhood is easy to find help from others; find job opportunities; training opportunities; find safe, pleasant and accessible green areas, participate in cultural events; find adequate social and health assistance, find a place to do sports, find healthy food, find children playgroups, moving on foot, moving by bike

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			(Qualitative and Quantitative /Self reported /Key Impact Indicator)
	Improved satisfaction with urban green areas (P)	Satisfaction with urban green areas	persons who are satisfied with public green areas of their neighborhood in terms of accessibility, safety, inclusiveness, beauty, comfort (Quantitative/Self reported / Key impact indicator)
	Increased inclusiveness of public squares and green areas (P; C)	Inclusiveness of public squares and green areas	Persons who feel free to access, to use and to move within the public squares and green areas in their neighborhood (Quantitative and qualitative/Self reported /Key Impact Indicator)
	Improved sense of belonging and satisfaction with the quality of the neighbourhood (P; C)	Sense of belonging and perception of the neighborhood	Number of persons who like their neighborhood; who think that it has a good reputation; who think that the image of the neighborhood has improved in the past two years; who think it could attract more tourists in the next years; who would not move to another neighborhood (Qualitative and Quantitative /Self reported /Key Impact Indicator)

IHW indicators: healthy lifestyles

Sub-dimension	Expected change (P=partners' view / C=citizens' view)	Indicator	Description
Physical health status	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Self-reported health status	Average level of physical health reported by persons on a 5 points scales (Quantitative/Self reported / context indicator)

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Determinants of health	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Practice of physical activity	frequency of practice of physical activity in a week (Quantitative /Self reported / context indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Time spent on food preparation at home	Average time spent by persons preparing their meals at home in a day (Quantitative/Self reported / context indicator)
	Increased consumption of self-grown fruit and vegetables	Self-grown fruit and vegetables consumption	persons who declare to consume self-grown fruit and vegetables (Qualitative/Self reported /Key Impact Indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Consumption of fruits and vegetables	persons who declare to consume fresh fruits and vegetables on a daily basis (Quantitative/Self reported / context indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Access to healthy and nutritious food	persons who were unable to eat healthy and nutritious food in the last week (Quantitative/Self reported / context indicator)
	Increased awareness and motivation towards healthy habits (P; C)	Awareness and motivation towards healthy habits	persons who are aware about healthy habits and motivated to change their lifestyles (Qualitative/self reported/ Key Impact Indicator)
Sports practice	Increased practice of sports in public green areas (P)	Practice of sports in public green areas	frequency of use of the public outdoor/green areas to do sports in a week (Quantitative and qualitative/Self reported / Key impact indicator)

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	Increased perception of benefits from sports (P)	Benefits from sports	persons who think that sports/physical activity contributes to their wellbeing (qualitative/Self reported /Key impact indicator)
Cultural consumption and production	Increased participation in cultural activities within public spaces (P; C)	Participation in cultural activities within public spaces (outdoor/indoor)	frequency of participation in cultural activities/consumptions in public squares, green areas, centers of their neighborhood in a week (Quantitative/Self reported / Key impact indicator)
	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Cultural consumptions	Average time devoted to cultural consumptions during the week (theatre, reading books, cinema, exhibitions) (Quantitative/self reported/context indicator)
	Increased local cultural engagement (P)	Local cultural engagement	Persons directly involved in the organization, production and management of cultural activities, products, places and events in their neighborhood (Quantitative self reported/ key impact indicator)
Leisure/Free time	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Time devoted to leisure and personal care	Average time (hours) devoted to leisure and personal care in a typical working day (Quantitative/Self reported / context indicator)
	Increased time spent playing relaxing or doing sports in public green areas (P)	time spent playing, relaxing or doing sports in public green areas	Average time (hours) spent playing, relaxing or doing sports in public green areas in a day (Quantitative/Self reported / Key impact indicator)

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Increased time spent in social and recreational public spaces (P)	time spent in social and recreational public spaces	Average time spent in social and recreational public spaces in a day (Quantitative/Self reported / Key impact indicator)
No change expected - context indicator (P)	Time devoted to family care	Average time in a day devoted to family care (Quantitative/Self reported / context indicator)
No change expected - context indicator (P)	Time devoted to pets' care/playing with pets	Average time devoted to pets' care/playing with pets in a day (Quantitative/Self reported / context indicator)
No change expected - context indicator (P)	Satisfaction with free time use	persons who are satisfied with the quality of their free time/the way they spend their free time (Quantitative/Self reported / context indicator)
Improved quality of one's free time in public spaces (C)	Perceived quality of free time in public spaces	Persons who think that the quality of their free time in public spaces is satisfactory (Qualitative self reported/key impact indicator)
Increased perception of benefits from social and recreational public spaces (P; C)	Benefits from social and recreational public spaces	persons who think that social and recreational public spaces contribute to their wellbeing (Qualitative self reported/key impact indicator)

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IHW indicators: economic well-being

Sub-dimension	Expected change (P=partners' view / C=citizens' view)	Indicator	Description
Employability	Increased employability of people (C)	Opportunity to find a job in the city	persons who are satisfied with the opportunities offered by the job market at city level (Qualitative/self reported/key impact indicator)
		Expected sector of occupation	persons who think they can find a job in NBS related sector in the next 6 months (Qualitative/self reported/key impact indicator)
	Increased satisfaction with one's skills and competences (P)	Satisfaction with one's own competencies, skills 1	persons who are satisfied with their level of skills and competences (Qualitative/self reported/key impact indicator)
		Satisfaction with one's own competencies, skills 2	Persons who think that their education, skills and competences will be helpful to find a paid job in the city (Qualitative/self reported/key impact indicator)
Financial situation	No change expected - context indicator (P)	Feeling that one's basic needs are met	persons who believe that their basics needs are sufficiently met (Quantitative/Self reported /context indicator)
	Increased satisfaction with one's surroundings and living environment (P; C)	Satisfaction with one's surroundings/living environment	satisfaction related to one's own surroundings/living environment (qualitative/Self reported /Key impact indicator)

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Appendix 4. Open call text

Aicinām pieteikties projekta IN-HABIT konsultatīvajā padomē!

Projekta “IN-HABIT: Veselīgas un iekļaujošas pilsētas” (www.inhabit-h2020.eu) komanda aicina pieteikties aktīvi darboties gribošus ar Āgenskalna apkaimi saistītus cilvēkus konsultatīvajā padomē, lai ar dažādu aktivitāšu palīdzību veidotu daudzfunkcionālu pārtikas centru ilgtspējīgi ražotai vietējai pārtikai Āgenskalna tirgus teritorijā, kas vienlaikus kalpotu kā atvērta, dažādu iedzīvotāju grupu satikšanās, izglītošanās un fizisku aktivitāšu telpa. Šī projekta virsmērķis ir uzlabot kopējo Āgenskalna apkaimes labklājību.

Pieteikšanās tiek izsludināta uz 7 padomes locekļu vietām. Dalība padomē ir vismaz uz vienu gadu, un tā ir brīvprātīga.

Mēs piedāvājam:

- Dalību starptautiskā projektā, kas apvieno četru Eiropas pilsētu (Rīga, Kordova, Piza, Nitra) pieredzes labklājības un veselības veicināšanā;
- iespēju uzlabot Āgenskalna apkaimes labklājību, veicināt iekļaujošu sabiedrību un veidot daudzfunkcionālu pārtikas centru Āgenskalna tirgū;
- Piedalīties projekta aktivitāšu atlasē, mērķu sasniegšanā un to izvērtēšanā;
- Strādāt kopā vienā komandā ar Baltic Studies Centre, Rīgas plānošanas reģionu un Āgenskalna tirgus komandu.

Pieteikšanās:

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Pieteikties aicināti Āgenskalna apkaimes attīstībā ieinteresēti un aktīvi cilvēki no dažādām sabiedrības grupām un organizācijām, aizpildot pieteikuma formu, aprakstot savu interesi, pieredzi un vīziju dalībai vismaz vienā no projektā plānotajām aktivitātēm Āgenskalna tirgus teritorijā:

1. Sporta un rotaļu aktivitāšu punkti ārā teritorijā;
2. Kopienas virtuves izveide;
3. Ilgtspējīga pārtikas atkritumu apsaimniekošana;
4. agenskalnatirgus.lv internetveikala attīstība.

Pieteikšanās no 15.02.-28.02.2021.

Saite uz pieteikumu: <https://ej.uz/pieteiksanaspadome>

Saite uz konsultatīvās padomes nolikumu: <https://ej.uz/padomesnolikums>

***IN-HABIT mērķis** ir veicināt iekļaujošu veselību un labklājību četrās mazās un vidējās pilsētās Eiropā – Kordovā (Spānija), Rīgā (Latvija), Lukā (Itālija) un Nitrā (Slovākija). Katrā pilsētā projekts izmantos līdz šim nepietiekami novērtētus resursus (kultūru, pārtiku, cilvēku-dzīvnieku saiknes un vidi), lai uzlabotu veselību un labklājību, īpašu uzmanību pievēršot dzimtes, iedzīvotāju dažādības, vienlīdzības un iekļautības aspektiem.*

Projekts sniegs inovatīvus risinājumus, kā veicināt veselību un labklājību kā kopēju sabiedrības resursu; attīstīs sociālo uzņēmējdarbību, kas ļauj nodrošināt iztiku un veicina veselīgāku dzīvesveidu; izstrādās aplikāciju, kas ļaus izmērīt projekta ietekmi un veicinās sabiedrības uzvedības izmaiņas u.c. Šie risinājumi tiks kopīgi izstrādāti, īstenoti un pārvaldīti ar vietējām ieinteresētajām personām. Projekta aktivitātes Rīgā tiks īstenotas pārtikas jomā. Āgenskalna tirgus teritorijā tiks veidots multifunkcionāls, iekļaujošs pārtikas centrs. Piecu turpmāko gadu laikā īstenojamās aktivitātes ietvers kopienas virtuves izveidi, inovatīvas atkritumu apsaimniekošanas salas izveidi, teritorijas labiekārtošanu bērnu un jauniešu auditorijai, kā arī interneta tirdzniecības

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platformas pilnveidi. Visu aktivitāšu izstrāde un ieviešana paredzēta ar sabiedrības līdzdalību, kā arī ar paralēlo izglītojošo programmu norisi.

Kontaktpersona jautājumiem par Konsultatīvās padomes darbu:

Una Meiberga, e-pasts: info@agenskalnatirgus.lv, tālrunis: 29402027

Organizāciju LOGO:

Projekta mājaslapa: <https://www.inhabit-h2020.eu/>

Projektu finansē:

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INHABIT projekts ir saņēmis Eiropas Savienības pētniecības un inovāciju atbalsta programmas „Apvārsnis 2020” finansējumu saskaņā ar līguma Nr. 869227

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Appendix 5. Results of the baseline study

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KEY FINDINGS FROM THE BASELINE STUDY - RIGA

> SOCIAL INCLUSION

People living or frequenting Āgenskalns neighbourhood experience **good and satisfactory social relations and higher social and civic engagement.**

> SPATIAL WELL-BEING

> ACCESSIBILITY OF RESOURCES IN THE NEIGHBOURHOOD

People living or frequenting Āgenskalns neighbourhood widely **appreciate the great accessibility of local resources**, particularly shops, healthy food, cultural and leisure opportunities, green areas and services.

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RIGA - 2

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KEY FINDINGS FROM THE BASELINE STUDY - RIGA

> SATISFACTION WITH THE NEIGHBOURHOOD AND URBAN GREEN AREAS

People living or frequenting Āgenskalns neighbourhood show a **good sense of belonging to the neighbourhood** and **appreciation of the quality of local public spaces and green areas**.

> PHYSICAL HEALTH AND HEALTHY LIFESTYLES

> HEALTHY HABITS

People living or frequenting Āgenskalns neighbourhood show a good level of **awareness and motivation toward healthy habits**, especially with regard to contact with nature, consumption of healthy food, use of public spaces for socialization, walking and relaxing.

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RIGA - 3

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KEY FINDINGS FROM THE BASELINE STUDY - RIGA

> LEISURE AND FREE TIME

Due to **Covid 19**, people living or frequenting Āgenskalns neighbourhood, **have increased the frequency of playing, relaxing or doing sports in public green areas** as well as the attendance at the **market as a social and recreational space**.

> MENTAL HEALTH

People living or frequenting Āgenskalns neighbourhood experience a **higher level of psychological well-being and a lower level of mental distress**.

> ECONOMIC WELL-BEING

People living or frequenting Āgenskalns neighbourhood express a comparable satisfaction with their financial situation. However, they are **concerned with the access to house and affordability of houses**.

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RIGA - 4

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